

REVIEW ON OINTMENT

***Khushbu Patel, Yani Patel, Kruti Patel, Vaishnavi Patel, Prachi Patel, Yashvi Patel,
Bhumi Patel**

Shri Sarvajanik Pharmacy College, Mehsana-1.

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***Corresponding Author**

Khushbu Patel

Shri Sarvajanik Pharmacy College,
Mehsana-1.

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ABSTRACT

Ointments are semisolid dosage form which usually act as Visco-elastic materials when shear stress is applied. They generally contain medicinal ingredients and are used to be applied externally to the body for therapeutic effect. Many therapeutic agents used for topical application to intact or broken skin or to mucous membranes are presented in the form of semisolid consistency variously designated as ointments, creams, pastes etc. It is used mainly as protective or emollient for the skin. The first step towards the goal is screening of plants used in popular medicine. Along with other dosage forms, herbal drugs also used in the form of ointment. Ointments made with an emulsion type base are called creams. Ointment agents since the aspects of liquid formulations mainly protect wounds, lubricate the skin and local treatment, etc.,

some drugs can have a local onset of action after transdermal absorption and can also produce systemic therapeutic effects. Therefore, ointment formulations have attracted much attention for their advantages of convenient use, stable properties, good dissolution properties, and are also one of the important directions in modern pharmaceuticals research.

KEYWORD

1. PEG: - Polyethylene glycol polymer
2. FDA: - Food Drug Administration
3. O/W: - Oil in Water
4. W/O: - Water in Oil
5. UV: - Ultraviolet

6. Brookfield Viscometer (DV-11+ PRO)

INTRODUCTION^[2-6]

- Ointments are homogeneous, semi solid preparation intended for external application to the skin or certain mucous membranes for emollient, protective, therapeutic or prophylactic purpose where a degree of occupation is desired.
- The active components or drugs in pharmaceutical formulations are designed to be delivered to the desired site and to have therapeutic effects.
- The Ointment meaning refers to the topical application of this formulation. An Ointment is prepared for applying on the skin and mucosal region of our body such as anywhere on the skin, chest, nose, anus, mucus membrane of eyes, etc. You will be astonished to know that an Ointment can be categorized as prescribed or over the counter drugs. Ointment formulation must have a base to disperse the therapeutic substance and to apply them on the topical portion of a human body. The preparation is not that simple as a complex base is prepared by mixing oil and water together.

Image 1: Ointment CLASSIFICATION OF OINTMENT.^[1]

1. Unmedicated Ointments

- These Ointments do not contain any drug.
- They are useful as emollients, protectants.
- Example: Petroleum jelly.

2. Medicated Ointments

- These Ointments contain drugs which show local or systemic effects.

TYPES OF OINTMENT BASE^[1]

1. Oleaginous Base (Hydrocarbon base)

- These bases are fats, fixed oil, hydrocarbon or silicones.
- They are anhydrous, greasy, non-washable does not absorb water and occlusive form a film on skin, so it increases the skin hydration by reducing the rate of loss of surface water.
- They should not be applied to infected skin. Eg- White petroleum.

2. Absorption Base

- Anhydrous but hydrophilic ointment bases, they can absorb several times their weight of water to form water-in-oil emulsion.
- They are non- washable, not water soluble.
- They used as protectant, emollient, vehicle for aqueous solution, solid, and non-hydrolysable drugs.
- Eg- hydrophilic petroleum.

3. Emulsion Base (Water removable Base)

- Emulsion base in Sub two parts:

A. W/O Emulsion Base

- These are anhydrous hydrophilic, absorbs water and non-water removable, with low thermal conductivity and occlusive.
- They have the same properties as the absorption base.
- Eg- Hydro cream.

B. O/W Emulsion Base

- These bases are anhydrous, water soluble, absorb water and water washable.
- They are either carbowaxes Polyethylene Glycols (PEGs) or hydrated gums.
- They are used as drug vehicles.
- Eg- Poly base.

4. Water soluble bases

- Water soluble bases contain only the water-soluble ingredients and not the fats or other greasy substance hence, they are known as grease less bases.
- Water soluble bases consist of water-soluble ingredients such as polyethylene glycol

polymer (PEG) which are popularly known as carbowaxes and commercial known as macrogols.

- Eg PEG ointment.

IDEAL PROPERTY OF OINTMENT^[1]

- They should be stable, neutral in reaction, nongreasy, non-irritating, nondehydrating, nonhygroscopic and water removable.
- They should be compatible with all medicines.
- They should be free from objectionable odour.
- They should act as vehicle for medicaments.
- They should be efficient on dry, oily or moist skins.
- They should be composed of readily available ingredients of known composition.
- They should be capable of holding at least 50 percent of water.
- They should be easily compounded by the pharmacist.
- They should get melted or softened at body temperature.

ADVANTAGES OF OINTMENT^[9]

- Handling of ointment is easier than bulky liquid dosage forms.
- They are chemically more stable than liquid dosage forms.
- They facilitate application of the directly to the effected body part and avoid exposure of other parts to the drug.
- They are suitable for patients who find it difficult to take the drugs by parenteral and oral routes.
- They prolong the contact time between the drug and effected area.
- The bioavailability of drug administered as Ointments is more since it prevents passage through liver.

DISADVANTAGES OF OINTMENT^[9]

- They are bulkier than solid dosage forms.
- When applications of an exact quantity of ointment to the affected area is required, it difficult to ascertain the same.
- They are less stable than solid dosage form.

EVALUATION OF OINTMENT^[12]

All the prepared ointments are characterized for the parameters such as appearance, Odor, colour, homogeneity, pH, spreadability, water number, and viscosity measurements.

1. Organoleptic characteristics

All blank formulation (i.e., formulations without active ingredient) and drug loaded formulations are tested for physical appearance, colour, texture, phase separation, and homogeneity. These characteristics are evaluated by visual observation. Homogeneity and texture are tested by pressing a small quantity of the formulated ointment between the thumb and index finger. The consistency of the formulations and the presence of coarse particles are used to evaluate the texture and homogeneity of the formulations. Immediate skin feels (including stiffness, grittiness, and greasiness) is also evaluated.

2. pH

About 2.5 g of all formulations are taken in dry beaker and 50 ml of water is added. Beaker containing ointment is heated on water bath at 60-70°C. The pH of ointments determined using a pH meter. The determinations are carried out in triplicate, and the averages of three readings were noted.

3. Spreadability

Spreadability of the formulation is determined by an apparatus suggested by Multimer with some modifications. It consists of a wooden block having a pulley at one end with fixed glass slide on block. An excess of ointment (3 g) placed on ground plate. The ointment is sandwiched between this plate and another glass plate having the dimension of fixed ground plate and provided with the hook. A 1 kg weight is placed on the top of the two plates for 5 min to expel air and to provide a uniform film of the ointment between the plates. Excess of ointment is scrapped off from the edges. The top plate is then subjected to pull of 240 g. With the help of spring attached to the hook and time required by the top plate to cover 10 cm was noted. A shorter interval indicates better spreadability. Spreadability is calculated using the following formula:

$$S = M \times L / T \text{ Where, } S = \text{Spreadability}$$

M = Weight in the pan (tied to the upper slide) L = Length moved by the glass slide and

T = Time (in seconds) taken to separate the slide completely each other.

4. Viscosity

Viscosity of ointment is carried out using Brookfield viscometer (DV-11+ PRO). LV spindle no.64 is used for the measurement of viscosity. Viscosity is measured at 10 rpm at room temperature.

5. Water number

Water number is the maximum amount of water that can be added to 100 g of base at a given temperature. It is determined by continuously stirring the base with the addition of distilled water. When no more water is absorbed into the base evidenced by droplets of water, remaining in the container is taken as end point.

6. Drug content

Content of Flurbiprofen in the formulation is determined by diluting 1 g of ointment equivalent to 2 mg of drug in 10 ml of ethanol and volume is made up to 100 ml with ethanol. Absorbance is measured at 275 nm using ultraviolet (UV) - visible spectrophotometer and percentage drug content is calculated, and average of three determination is noted.

7. In vitro diffusion study

Franz diffusion cell is used for the drug release studies. Ointment is evenly applied into the surface of cellulose membrane. The cellulose membrane is clamped between the donor and the receptor chamber of diffusion cell. The receptor compartment is filled with phosphate buffer pH 7.4, and the assembly is maintained at $37^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 5$ under constant magnetic stirring. With reference to Scale-up and post approval changes guidelines laid by FDA, 300mg of ointment is applied to the membrane on the donor compartment and then covered with aluminium foil to prevent drying out. Aliquots are withdrawn at predetermined time intervals over a period of 1 h and amount of drug release is analysed at 275 nm using UV spectrophotometer.

GENERAL TECHNIQUES FOR PREPARATION OF OINTMENT^[1,13-14]

1. Mechanical Incorporation Method

The mechanical incorporation method of ointment preparation involves thoroughly mixing components into an ointment base using tools like a mortar and pestle or a glass slab and spatulas until a uniform, smooth product is achieved. This process requires initial grinding and mixing of powders or incorporating gummy materials into the base, potentially using a levigating agent to reduce particle size, before blending the entire mixture to ensure even

distribution of the drug throughout the base.

Steps of the Incorporation Method

- 1. Prepare Ingredients:** Powdered ingredients are reduced to fine particles. Gummy materials may be dissolved in a solvent before incorporation.
- 2. Levigations (If Necessary):** Solid ingredients can be levigated by mixing them with a small amount of the base or a compatible vehicle (like glycerine) to form a smooth dispersion, which prevents a gritty texture in the final product.
- 3. Initial Mixing:** A small portion of the levigated powder or the entire powder is mixed with a small portion of the ointment base on the slab or in the mortar until a uniform mixture is achieved.
- 4. Gradual Incorporation:** The remaining base is then added gradually, and the mixing process is continued until the entire mixture is thoroughly and uniformly blended.
- 5. Final Spatulation/Mixing:** The prepared portions are combined and worked with the spatula, or the entire mixture is worked, until the product is smooth, uniform, and free of gritty particles.

A. Trituration Method

The trituration method for preparing ointments involves grinding solid active ingredients into a very fine powder, then levigating it with a small amount of the ointment base to form a smooth paste. Finally, the remaining base is gradually incorporated into this paste using vigorous trituration with a spatula or mortar and pestle until a uniform, homogeneous ointment is achieved. This technique is ideal for small-scale preparation and ensures even dispersion of the medicament.

Steps for the Trituration Method

- 1. Powder the Medicament:** Start by reducing the solid medicinal ingredients to a very fine powder, typically using a mortar and pestle. The goal is to significantly reduce the particle size of the powder.
- 2. Levigate the Powder:** On an ointment slab, take a small portion of the ointment base and triturate it with the fine powder. Use a stainless-steel spatula or the mortar and pestle for this step.
- 3. Incorporate the Base:** Add the rest of the ointment base gradually in small quantities. Continue triturating with the spatula or by using the mortar and pestle.
- 4. Achieve Uniformity:** Triturate the mixture thoroughly until the medicament is

completely and uniformly distributed throughout the base. This creates a smooth, homogeneous ointment.

- 5. Incorporate Liquids (if any):** If liquid ingredients are part of the formulation, they are incorporated last by spatulation or by using the mortar and pestle for better containment.

B. Emulsification Method

Ointment emulsification involves preparing either a water-in-oil (W/O) or oil in-water (O/W) emulsion by simultaneously heating and stirring the oil-soluble and water-soluble components, respectively, until they are uniform. The external phase is then slowly added to the internal phase with continued vigorous stirring to create the emulsion, which is then cooled.

Steps for the Emulsification Method

1. Preparation of the Phases

- **Oil Phase:** All oil-soluble components are dissolved in the oil base. If necessary, ingredients are melted using a water bath.
 - **Aqueous Phase:** Water-soluble components, including emulsifiers and stabilizers, are dispersed in water. Heating may be used to accelerate their dissolution.
- 2. Temperature Adjustment:** Both the oil and aqueous phases are heated to approximately 70°C over a water bath to ensure that all waxes are melted and the phases are at the same temperature for proper mixing.
 - 3. Forming the Emulsion:** The internal phase is then slowly and continuously added to the external phase with vigorous stirring. The mixture is then cooled with continuous stirring until it congeals.

4. Equipment Used

Beakers

Mortars and pestles

High-shear mixers (especially for commercial production)

2. Fusion Method

The fusion method for preparing ointments involves melting all or some ointment base components together, typically using a water bath, and then incorporating the drug or medicament by stirring the mixture until it congeals into a homogeneous product. High-melting-point components are melted first, with heat-sensitive and volatile ingredients added last at a lower temperature to prevent degradation and ensure a stable, uniform ointment.

Procedure for the Fusion Method

- 1. Melt the Base:** Heat the ointment base components in order of their melting points, starting with the highest melting point ingredient and progressing to the lowest. Using a water bath is recommended to prevent overheating.
- 2. Incorporate Solid Medicaments:** Add the solid drug or medicament to the melted base. For more thorough incorporation, the solid should be added in decreasing order of melting point, as noted for the base.
- 3. Add Liquids:** If the ointment contains liquid or water-soluble components, these should be heated to a temperature like the melted base before being incorporated.
- 4. Stir and Cool:** Stir the entire mixture continuously until it congeal into a homogeneous mass.
- 5. Add Volatile and Heat-Sensitive Substances:** Add any volatile materials (like certain essential oils) or heat-sensitive ingredients last, once the mixture has cooled sufficiently.
- 6. Congeal:** Continue stirring the mixture until it cools and a uniform product is formed.

CONCLUSION

Ointment is semi-solid topical preparations offering therapeutic benefits through local protection, lubrication, and drug delivery, with advantages including ease of use, good stability, and flexible formulation bases like petrolatum or those containing sunflower wax. Ointment research continues to explore new bases and manufacturing technologies, such as hot-melt extrusion, to enhance drug release profiles and efficiency, making ointments a key area in modern pharmaceuticals.

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